

Women
In CTRL

100 WOMEN

WHAT IT MEANS TO HAVE
A SEAT AT THE TABLE

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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From my own experiences in the music industry, this has made me aware of the inequality and barriers, which exists for all women, especially women of colour.

Jin Jin

**Songwriter /
Jinsing Publishing Ltd./
Senior A&R Parlophone
IVORS Board Director**

A full representation of women, brings with it different experiences and knowledge. Whilst trying to break into the music industry I personally wasn't aware of any Black female staff, at senior level at that time, who could provide me with advice or much needed mentorship.

When the opportunity arose, I made the decision to sit on the prestigious Ivor's Board, as I wanted to connect with other music creators and to have a voice in the decision making process. This position has not only given me the opportunity to continue to push for change, but also to be involved in the process of steering the career paths of other individuals. It is important to see a cross section of people in higher positions in today's modern and diverse society.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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It means to have an active and respected voice that serves as catalyst for change and is a motivation and encouragement to others, especially women across this industry.

Afryea Henry-Fontaine

Marketing Director

Motown UK/EMI

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Kanya King CBE
Founder & CEO
MOBO Group

A seat at the table means that you are part of the conversation, are being heard and can provide and have access to opportunities. The way to get a seat at the table when you are not invited or welcomed is to create the changes you want to see in the world. Do not wait for the invitation, be part of the solution.

This is why we created MOBOLISE, a career networking platform built by Accenture, to be a solution to the diversity challenges within the workforce, as well as providing access to jobs, personal growth, content and rare mentorship opportunities as well as network with other industry professionals.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Aluna Francis
Artist/
FAC Board Observer

Now that I'm part of a board (FAC) that makes it their business to find out what's happening for artists in the industry and where changes can actually be made it has changed my attitude.

I used to just accept the way things were, now I know what's going on and I can contribute to making change on a wider scale.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Lara Baker

**Director of Business Development,
UK & IE
Songtrust**

The only way to make the music industry a more inclusive and safe place for the young women and people of minorities who are entering it is by having more diversity at the top. As an industry, we need women and people of colour to have seats at the table, to be leaders and decision makers, in order to change the culture for the generations to come. To me, having a seat at the table gives me the chance to help create a more diverse, inclusive and safe industry than the one I joined.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Having a seat at the table means having the ability to be seen, heard and to have influence in my sector. Being able to infiltrate areas which can often be exclusive is why having a seat at the table and bringing others in is so important

Mahaliah Edwards

Violinist / Educator

ISM Board

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Jackie Davidson MBE
**JD Management/
PPL Board/
MPA Board**

To anyone thinking about going forward for boards, I would say go for it! Don't feel intimidated, you're there to add your perspective and bring change. It may take the first 12 months for you to feel comfortable speaking, that's ok. Read your board papers thoroughly before each meeting, prepare, and don't be afraid to ask questions.

To those that have been sitting on the same boards for 15+ years, I would say: You have a responsibility to pass on knowledge and prepare the next generation to follow you. It is essential that you adopt a more diverse and inclusive approach. Inclusion should be afforded to all, regardless of one's gender, ethnicity or background.

If all else fails, sometimes we need to destroy the table and build a whole new one.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Sheryl Nwosu

Lawyer & Chair of
the Black Music Coalition

Having a seat at the proverbial table to me means being in a position to speak and actually be heard. It means being in a position to advocate in places where I can affect change.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Sian Anderson

**DJ / Marketing Manager
Saint Music**

It's easy for companies to react to uproar when reports show they lack diversity or lack women in senior roles by just employing more women, but having a seat at the table doesn't just mean employment to me, it means being able to speak at the table and have your voice heard in key conversations and listened too when it comes to big decision making.

That's when we're really at the table, and that's what I'd like to see more of.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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ECKOES

**Artist /
FAC Board**

Having a Seat at the Table means having a voice where the decisions are made, not just a voice from which profit can be extracted.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Being recognised as a valuable voice in any conversation and subsequently invited to join a group of my peers around 'The Table', means there is the potential for racial equity in areas of the industry. It's a lonely and hard task at times, but a necessary one.

Yvette Griffith

**Co-Chief Exec & Executive
Director
Jazz re:refreshed
AIM Board**

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Being a wheelchair user, I bring my own seat to the table. It saves waiting to be asked. I bring the disability perspective. I'm unapologetic. It's still missing from the Boardroom,

Suzanne Bull MBE

Founder

Attitude is Everything

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Colleen Theis
COO
The Orchard

Being empowered to drive visions to reality, with a unique perspective that adds resonance and relevance in what's largely still a man's world. I was once quoted as saying "If you don't have a seat at the table, you're probably on the menu!" I decided to make my own table long ago, rather than wait for a seat to open up. Thankfully that table is now banquet-sized and full of amazing people who make every day fun.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Kate Reilly

Director of People and
Organisational Development
PPL

Sometimes it is about knowing your own worth and having the confidence to put yourself forward for a seat at the table, I have definitely had my moments of imposter syndrome. It's about surrounding yourself with allies to champion you and others being open to change. We all benefit from diversity of thought!

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

Kelli-Leigh

**Artist / Songwriter
FAC Board Observer**

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I'm really proud to have worked with the MU & The FAC to create the 'session musician or featured artist' guidance document which will now help create real clarity for so many creatives in recording work. Being a board observer for the FAC has been brilliant to be a part of the wider conversation and discussions that affect artists daily, like topics including the streaming enquiry. I feel the voices of female and diverse background candidates being brought onto music industry boards is paramount in gaining fresh perspective and real knowledge on how to make the industry a better place for all involved

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Nicole McKenzie

**Co-founder, Creative Director
& Head of Promotions
MIC Records / Atles Music
AIM Board**

It's everything - it's about been represented, being seen and heard. It means growth and positive change. Lessons can be learned from hearing a range of diverse voices, it's simply not good enough to have one voice to speak for a particular group.

From an individual perspective it new pathways being open to you, promoting a positive self-image, and the opportunity to listen and communicate. As a business owner, it means knowledge and fresh ideas, new possibilities and staying current.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Michelle Escoffery

**Songwriter/
President of
PRS Members' Council**

In order to successfully and authentically represent, support and develop all aspects of the music industry, we must reflect the same. It is not only important, but absolutely vital and should be a norm for different voices, perspectives, backgrounds, cultural experiences to be required at the table, to shape, guide, advocate and innovate for our sector now and always.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Naomi Pohl

**Deputy General Secretary
Musicians' Union**

Being an equal at the top table, whether on a board or in senior management, is hugely important. Being recognised for my knowledge and experience in its own right, beyond my gender and any form of tokenism, is something I and all women should be able to take for granted. Sadly that's not always the case, even now. We still have a way to go to remove barriers and achieve proper representation in our industry.

I hope that women already in senior roles and at board level demonstrate what's possible, and flag to women earlier on in their careers that they shouldn't wait politely to be asked but they should push forward in their careers confident of what they have to offer.

We should raise each other up.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Joanne Croxford

**Production Co-ordinator
Wellness + Diversity Specialist
Live Touring
Global Touring Office (GTO)**

Being able to inform change based on the lived experience of myself as a queer woman in the industry and that of others - making decisions about people, with them in the room.

I believe the biggest threat to the industry as we know it is the lack of diversity. Be this gender diversity, ethnic diversity or socio-economic diversity - we are the sum of our parts and the more we are inclusive and help people to feel belong once they get here, the more likely we are to be as diverse (+ interesting!), as the music fans we are all desperate to serve!

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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It means access - to information, to decision making and to people of influence. It provides an opportunity for me to champion those whose voices and stories are not ordinarily heard or considered.

Nike Durosaro

**Music Manager/ Music
Industry Consultant/
Big Drum Entertainment
MMF Board**

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Jasmine Dotiwala
Multimedia broadcaster
Activist

Having a seat at the table means not just being invited to sit at the table, but to dance, eat, speak and interact at the dinner party. It means my voice is heard, trusted, valued and celebrated equally to everyone else's.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Laughta

Artist/ Music Producer

Presenter, Represent Radio

A seat at the table means having equal say and not being on the sidelines observing. It's time for change, It's really time to stop with performative antics and it's time for women!

Companies that realise the power of diversity of thought around the table, will be the winners, creating inclusive cultures where people feel accepted, included and can learn from each other.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Indy Vidyalkara

PR & Diversity Consultant
Founder- Independent PR
UK Music Diversity Taskforce
Board member BPI EJAG
Board member PIPA

Having a seat at the table is having a voice when previously my voice was not heard, or nobody even knew I was in the room waiting for my seat, my turn. Being a woman in music with over twenty years in the industry, I first entered the industry seeing very few women who looked like me in high positions to aspire to. No real sisterhood to support me, to lift me up, relate to my experience and give me guidance. It was an industry where resilience, determination and perseverance, sheer sweat and graft was required to stay and succeed if you looked like me. Thankfully those times are changing and women like me are valued, our voices, our insight, our opinions, our experience is valued and sought after on boards and in organisations. We bring others through and we act as beacons. It's an exciting time of change, and long may it continue, but our work is far from done, the stats are still stark and show the huge gaps and disparities, be it career progression, pay gaps, or even the parenting penalty. By having a seat at the table, I am committed to use my voice as a force for good and I urge every woman with influence in the industry to do the same.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Vick Bain

Music Industry Consultant
vbain consulting
ISM Board

It's vitally important women are promoted and supported in their music industry careers as the statistics show we are not there yet in sufficient numbers or when we do we don't stay as long as the men around us. My involvement in the ISM is an absolute pleasure as it's got a long and authentic culture of involving women throughout its membership to its board, management team and CEO and I believe that is an inspiration to the rest of the music industry, most of which is still very male dominated.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Harriet JW

Founder
Secret Sessions &
GIRLS TO THE FRONT

Having a seat at the table is simply about equality, it means that on a fundamental level we believe that all humans deserve equal treatment, no matter who or what they are. To me this is pretty basic human rights but unfortunately we still have to fight for it. In order for us to progress the table must be diverse and amplify the voices of a wide cross section of society.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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To have a seat at the table is to be seen, to have a chance to be heard and the opportunity to make change. These boards should reflect the industry they serve.

Nadu Placca

Global Event & Experience

Architect

The Zoo XYZ

Black in the Boardroom

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Anna Gruszka

Label Partnerships

Manager UK

TikTok

It means bringing more chairs and redesigning the table. There's space for everyone, and there's definitely enough space for more women in the leadership roles in the music industry. Old shape of the table shouldn't restrict the present and the future.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Maxie Gedge

**Keychange Project Manager
PRS Foundation**

To me, having a seat at the table means not just being seen but being heard and valued. It's an important acknowledgement of how essential it is that we work hard to question who is not in the room and why - to make sure we are not just aiming for representation, but inclusion.

In my role at Keychange, gender mainstreaming is such an important part of the positive action we're working on. Women, gender minorities and all equity-seeking groups need to be involved in decision-making and policy-shaping so that structures are not 'adjusted' for us, they're BUILT for us. The structures (and the tables!) will be stronger if they're built for everyone.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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It carries a double meaning for me - it's about diversity and responsibility. I am hyper aware of the fact that more diversity means a better outcome and I feel a great responsibility to stand up for that.

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Magdalena Jensen

Creative Director &
Transformational Coach,
Chimes

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Gee Davy

COO

**AIM (Association of
Independent Music)**

For too long, having a seat at the table has meant women working harder than and having to fit in with, behave, speak and lead like men. That has resulted again and again in very few women being offered a seat at the table and countless talented women leaving the industry, exhausted by leading a double life and overdelivering. This is compounded when that woman isn't from the majority culture of the industry or the nation and has to put their cultural differences aside in order to take part and be heard.

Even now, when some progress is being seen, most of the women who drive the success of the UK music industry (and there are many - with more and more nominations made each year to the Music Week 'Women In Music Awards) are not seen or heard in decision-making. Truly having a seat at the table means recognising that many women look, sound, make decisions and lead differently to men, that boardrooms and work styles need to adapt to women, not the other way around. And once you get a seat at the table, using your voice and your difference to create more seats at more tables. It is enough to be yourself, you have earned a seat at the table. Fight your imposter syndrome, speak your truth and do things YOUR way!

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Bina 'Bob' Mistry

**Founder of music:defined /
Senior Counsel for
International Music & Business
Relations at Peloton**

I want to be seen and heard. I've been in the industry for 20 years, and I don't think I've ever had to fight as hard as I do now. Being recognised for commitment, hard work and energy injected into the industry I'm so passionate about.

Having a seat at the table means that I can share experience, knowledge and lessons with the next generation of music execs. For me, I want young aspiring brown girls to look up and know they can do it too. I didn't have that, and I still don't... I'm still trying to carve my path.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Reju Sharma

Marketing & Promotions

Manager

Armada Music UK

Every area in the music and media industry I've worked in or with peers of protected characteristics, it's notable that our work has increased innovation, authentic cultural connection for audiences and attracted diverse talent by developing long lasting stories that have impacted on cultural and creative change. These wins are celebrated by those who already have a seat at the table, but we should be able to have the voice to champion our own wins and continue to create change and growth from our lived, learned and authentic experiences.

The challenge here is to support, mentor and nurture the existing skill set of these women so we have the confidence and ability to not only be invited and seated but to be heard at the table.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Having a seat at the table means regarding my talent, experiences, perspective and ideas as just as valuable as those of my male counterparts.

Carla Monroe
Artist and Songwriter

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Amanda Maxwell

Artist Manager

Chair to UK Music Futures Board

EJAG board to the BPI

It means to champion and represent the marginalised voices that you don't normally see at board room level myself included. I love to have the conversations we do from a diverse board level - it leaves my brain firing with ideas, wanting to build connections and champion the work we are all doing to see fairer representation for the world we live in!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Clare McKinney
Head of Creative &
Commercial Development
Domino Music Group
AIM Board

A colleague suggested I put myself forward for the AIM board, I definitely needed the nudge, and am glad that I did it. The board has strong female representation. Meetings are respectful and everyone has a voice. More women on boards means that those women gain experience, it is a positive feedback. Ultimately it means we will be operating at the highest level and bringing a different perspective to problem solving.

If you don't have someone to nudge you, still consider putting yourself forward. Give yourself permission to have the opportunity. Our male peers are (mostly) a little more assured of their right to a position and won't think twice.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Having a Seat at The table means being represented, respected and heard.

Jenna G

Independent Artist

Running With Wolves LTD.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Carol Zuma-Hall
Finance Lead
Platoon

Having a seat at the table is extremely important because the music industry is made up of such a diverse melting pot of so many different types of people. It is only fair that that diversity is mirrored in the group of people who manage/steer the direction of the industry.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Andrea de Leon
Senior A&R Manager
UK & Europe
Audio Network

Having a seat at the table means occupying spaces where you can affect change. Pushing business and society towards a more equitable reality whilst having visibility to inspire and realise your own ambitions in whichever way you see fit.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Karma Bertelsen

**Audience Insights
Manager,
FUGA**

Having the hard work of my underrepresented peers (people of colour, women, non-binary, LGBTQI+) being recognised and being given the same privileges, salaries and opportunities to leadership positions as anyone else.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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If you are at the table at least you will know what's on the menu and have a choice rather than someone else choosing for you. There is power in being present.

**Wozzy Brewster,
OBE FRSA**

**Executive Director /Artist Manager
The Midi Music Company
Chainska Brassika**

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Jude McCardle
Membership Manager
AIM

If more women, black women and gender minorities have a 'seat at the table', we have the representation part which is so important. But do we have the inclusion part too? It's not automatic. That table has to be set up in a way that allows everyone to work and contribute to their full potential. We need to go further and rethink the end goal of a traditional Board - the culture within it, the personality traits that can typically be a requirement to get a seat and the qualities needed to thrive once they're at that table.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Bee Adamic
CEO
Liberty Music PR

To me it means having a voice, and a presence so that I'm seen and heard. But also that my opinions and ideas are valued and respected. That I'm able to positively influence and inspire those around it.

By having a Seat at the Table, I will endeavour to push boundaries and strive for positive change and put a much needed spotlight on issues that need to be addressed.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Emily Moxon

Managing Director,
Brownswood
Recordings /
AIM Board

Serving on the AIM Board has been a good experience. It has allowed me to take a more helicopter view of the industry, and exposed me to many new ideas. I have also met some incredibly smart people from across the independent sector. It has been a pleasure to see this particular table progressively diversify over my 4 years on the board, and the thinking, conversation and outcomes have undoubtedly benefitted from this change.

Being the person who is bringing diversity to any table can be quite challenging - however its when we get out of our comfort zones that we can start to create real change.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Vanessa Bakewell

**Client Partner
Facebook**

It's vitally important to have a seat at the table and to use that opportunity wisely. To then be an ally to the people around you. To champion the women around you. There is nothing more rewarding than celebrating the successes of your colleagues and peers and helping people rise in the industry. Those with a seat currently, need to be an ally, drive forward and accelerate much needed change as quickly as possible in the industry.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Emma Moore

**Artist Manager/
Music Business
Student**

Women hold the weight of the world, and the industry. It would not hold the same magic without the talent, creativity, intellect, support, and hard work of women, and it is important that this hard work is respected and celebrated. For me, having a seat at the table means having the ability to not only have our own voices heard, but the voices of our sisters too. When one of us wins, we all win.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Charlotte Caleb

**Director, BI, Data and
Channel Optimisation
AWAL**

As a new mum and a woman working in data I never would have even thought I would be where I am now. I am fearless now and always willing to put myself out there to push the industry forward. I hope other woman can see that and keep striving forward too.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Farah Syed

Manager, PR & Industry
Relations
Beatport

In order for a company to be truly diverse, decision-makers need to be diverse and inclusive. It is crucial and sets the tone for the company culture to thrive and evolve. I am proud to be a woman of colour working in the music industry for 13 years. I hope I can be a role-model and inspiration to other women of colour trying to move up the career ladder as we certainly need to amplify more diverse voices. It is not just important to have a Seat at the Table, it is essential. That way we can give our views and perspectives so conversations are well-rounded as well as fair. As Ruth Bader Ginsburg said best, "Women belong in all places where decisions are being made. It shouldn't be that women are the exception."

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Elinore Giles

Owner / Manager

Step Music Management

MMF Board

It allows me to advocate for the forgotten voices. To question the status quo, to allow women to realise they can stand up and have a voice and to never think their voice is not important, it's vital.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Frankie Wells

Co-Founder &
Station Manager
foundation.fm

It means being heard. So often I feel like I am filling a space, a tick box, but rarely do I feel heard. At least not the first time. I have to shout, I have really sell myself, to at least be heard maybe the third or fifth time. A seat at the table for me means there will be more and more seats for women, queer and non binary folk who need to be heard.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Golchehr Ghavami

**Live Sector Advisor @ AFEM
Artist Developer
Founding Committee Member
& Cultural Ambassador for
EarthPercent,
GEIST Agency**

Sexism and the lack of diversity within electronic music is irrefutable. Sexual harassment, hostile work environments and subtle biases are still obstacles, and women of color face even further obstacles to their advancement and, as a result, are even less likely to move into leadership roles.

The qualities of a leader - as well as the path to achieve leadership roles - are still largely based on an outdated male model that shuts women out, and because men have been leaders for so long, the traits associated with leadership are often thought of as masculine and not viewed as favorably when exhibited by women.

In this uphill battle women must advocate for themselves, so having a Seat at the Table means working against the impact of implicit bias and breaking subconsciously held stereotypes for a more inclusive and diverse future generation of movers and shakers.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Katie Sallows

General Manager
IMS

To many organisations 'Diversity & Inclusion' is just a concept, they talk the talk but if you look at their leadership or board of directors its a different story. Having a 'seat at the table' hopefully helps to demonstrate to other women coming up through the industry that they have a place and they belong here just as much as anyone else.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Annique Simpson
Music journalist
Freelance

To me, having a seat at the table means you get a real opportunity to share your ideas, insights and opinions in influential spaces. Emphasis on the real. If folks already at the table don't listen to you or view you as their equal, the seat is pointless. You might as well build a table for yourself!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Cilla Raie

Artist/ Songwriter

CR Records/

R.O.A.D. Entertainment

Having a Seat At The Table means being given the space to have open and honest conversations with no judgement. For me being able to express myself and shed light onto the issues we often face, means that it will not go unnoticed anymore. There is value in being able to have a safe and understanding space where real change can begin.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Michelle Yuen

**Business Intelligence Analyst
Chartmetric**

That change is really happening and that important and necessary voices that have not been properly represented for far too long are actually being heard - too often companies and businesses will make statements and declarations, but once the trend passes there is a distinct void of lasting impactful action. There are so many reasons why women should have a seat at the table, from greater innovation, wider perspective, and higher productivity to more empathy, greater social equity, and leading the next generation by showing that a difference can and is being made.

The evidence is irrefutable so the next step must be for more change to happen at these tables.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Laura May
Founder, May Music
Limited
MPA Board

I ran for the board because I felt that small and newly established publishers need representation and earning my Seat at the Table was a very proud moment. I have felt that with everything taking place in a virtual world I perhaps haven't been as involved or vocal as I might have been but there is still time. I have a bunch to learn and a lot to give.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Nicole Barsalona

**President,
Women in Music;
Artist Manager, Everyday
Rebellion**

For a long time, having a seat at the table implied that someone was doing you a favor by inviting you into the conversation. Today, I think it means being a valued and prioritized member of a community, where your opinion and your expertise is sought out. I won't sit at a table where I don't feel welcome, and lucky for me, there are a lot of seats at a lot of tables hosted by some really wonderful human beings who are creating the kind of change we all want to see in our industry, and beyond.

So, a seat at the table for me means sitting amongst friends and colleagues who inspire me, who do great work, and who I enjoy growing alongside. Those old tables where inclusivity and respect was not at the forefront? They're going to have a lot of empty seats!

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Having a seat at the table represents a significant step on the journey to a fully inclusive and equitable music industry, one in which all women are fully able to contribute to the ongoing discussions by speaking out and being heard!

Sally Anne Gross

**Course Leader -
Researcher/Author Music
Business Management MA
University of Westminster**

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Carla Brown

**Director
Syncdin**

Being heard - women are often overlooked in industries that are male dominated. It's important to have a voice and input, we play major roles behind and in front of the scenes.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Cat Park
Director
**Ten Letter PR/
Ten Letter Radio**

Having a Seat at the Table is of paramount importance. To have a voice, to have a space to share realities and to be represented as the person I am, which includes beliefs, opinions and experiences, ensures that I am not overlooked. By having a Seat at the Table we not only get to share different perspectives, create opportunities and bring a wealth of untapped experience to the forefront, but we also get to hold others accountable and have difficult conversations. So what does having a Seat at the Table mean to me? It means growth, inclusion and evolution.

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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I sit on the Board of the Music Publisher's Association (MPA) U.K. because diversity, in all its forms, is the bedrock of good decision making.

Catherine Manners

**Company Founder
& Director
Manners McDade
MPA Board**

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What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

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Carol Jack
Vocal Coach

I believe it's important not just to have a seat at their table but to have our own table. Women need to be in positions of power to bring balance and a different perspective to the business place, and to help ensure that women are treated with respect at all levels.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Niki Evangelou

Co-Founder

The Cat's Mother Network

Having a seat at the table for me is about being heard and often being a single voice for many. It's about doing your best to make sure that those who look like you, sound like you, and have faced or continue to face the same challenges that you have, are represented and included across the board. Decisions should be made only when there is diversity of skill, thought and lived experience, we shouldn't be settling for anything less in my eyes.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Noelle Scaggs

Founder and Co-Lead
Diversify The Stage
Fitz & The Tantrums

Having a seat at the table lends me the ability to contribute not only my voice and influence action to help reshape the current construct, but also shows others who reflect my background and identity that it is possible to do the same.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

The chance to make real change by being visible in a position of power. The chance to have people sit up, listen and take concrete action to diversify the electronic music industry as a matter of priority.

Samantha Warren

**Professor / Co-Chair of AFEM D&I
working group**

**Uni of Portsmouth/ Association for
Electronic Music**

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Namywa

**Artist and Founder
Girl Grind UK CIC**

Having a seat at the table for me or any woman is an opportunity to influence, decide and in some ways control the state of play. Having a seat at the table to me means more women and girls have thoughtful and healthful choices made with, by and for them, that greatly impact the dynamics of the future industries for women, girls, non binary people and men.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

For women to be treated equally by being listened to, included in and influencing decisions made by having the same opportunity as everyone else there.

Rebecca Davies-Cooke

**General Manager
Downtown Music Services**

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Neelofer Nova

**Poet, Writer,
Spoken Word Artist
Freelance Creative**

The music industry is a microcosm of wider society and it doesn't always favour women with the same representation, voice or opportunities. Having a seat at the table is lifeblood for the creative genius that we hold as women and a confirmation that women like me hold valid and worthy space, despite the challenges and a way to shine a light for other women to learn from our experiences. Unity and mutual support is vital for our success and I'm here for it!!!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Rosie Turner
Co-Founder
InChorus & EMII

For far too long there has been a dismal lack of diversity represented at board level. Ensuring that this changes, and that underrepresented groups have a seat at the table is critical to shaping a music industry that reflects the diversity we see in society at large. For me, having a seat at the table is also about increasing our ability to hold the industry to account around its culture & diversity, something Nadia's work with WIC and EMII shows is much needed.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Lynden Campbell

**Managing Director
Hot House Music**

Having a Seat at the Table means we have an opportunity to future proof business by actively embracing partnerships. To succeed we need diversity and inclusion. To achieve this we have to break down industry silos and work in partnership with each other. We have to openly discuss our fears and anxieties in order to create more effective business actions.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Yasmin Lajoie

Artist Manager

Slay

Having a seat at the table means more than being in the room. It's about being invited to speak, and feeling seen and heard. We need people in positions of influence to create space for us so we can affect change and ensure more equitable outcomes for everyone.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Sadiyya Moosa

Patel

**Solicitor/Founder/Creator of
Fashion Brand SMP London**

I should have a seat at the table irrespective of my gender, race and age. I'm strong and resilient and if there's no seat at the table, I'll make my own. We were born without limits and therefore we should be able to conquer without limits. Do not tell me I can't when I can. There's room for EVERYONE.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Kerry Harvey-Piper

**Co-Founder
Red Grape Music Ltd. /
MMF Board**

Having previously been on the Board of AIM and currently an MMF Board member, I've seen first hand how vital it is to have more women in positions where they can confidently raise and discuss a broad range of topics and crucially be part of the decision making process. Some of our issues are shared by our male counterparts, but some are not and would not necessarily occur to the men around the table. Bringing a wide selection of experiences, voices and diversity to the table enriches our industry, makes it more robust and resilient and builds a fairer, more equitable future for everyone.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Rachael Patterson

**Head of Artist Management,
K7 Music
AIM Board**

Having a seat at the table, having diverse board rooms and teams all the way from senior staff to those gaining new experience, besides being the most just way to operate, also makes the most sound business sense. Only with a wide range of knowledge, culture and life experience, with minds that think differently from one another and offer a whole variety of skills, can an industry thrive and move forward in this ever changing 21st century.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Selina Wedderburn

Head of Operations

Your Army

In order to make effective changes, we need more women to have a ‘Seat at the Table’. Last year’s report from Women in CTRL was an eye-opener. A diverse board provides an opportunity for women to speak about important changes that need to happen, to ensure a variety of perspectives are integrated and considered before making important decisions, particularly to improve diversity within the music industry.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

The fact that we have to even have this conversation is so embarrassing. The last thing I heard is that there are more women in the world than men. So make it make sense. Change is a common theme atm, so let's hurry up and change this.

Shahlaa Tahira

Presenter and Content Creator

**BBC/ Sony Music/
Somethin Else**

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

I feel that anytime a woman stands up and is counted, she makes that stand for all women...a quote I love is, 'a woman who knows what she brings to the table is not afraid to eat alone.'

Neesha Sharma

**Fashion Stylist /
Creative Director**

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Beverly Keel

Dean, College of Media and
Entertainment, Middle
Tennessee State University

Having a seat at the table is vital so that our voices are heard and our experiences and perspectives are taken into consideration when decisions are made. Without a seat at the table, we don't get a say in what and how decisions are made. Real and lasting change won't happen without it. Otherwise, women and/or people of color are either forgotten completely in the decision-making process or they must have others decide what is best for them.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

MIRI

Artist & Songwriter

An opportunity to be seen and heard in order to create real change. Conversations and platforms to discuss diversity and gender balance away from the table are majorly important but if we personally don't have a seat we don't have a say in the industry and it will be the same people making the same decisions.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Paula Wolfe

**Artist/ Producer/ Author
Academic/ Public Speaker
Sib Records**

Having a seat at the table means having a voice to represent not only the issues that have accompanied your own experiences as a woman in music but those experienced by others - especially those who lack the confidence or the means to voice those issues themselves.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Stevie Smith

CEO

**Americana Music
Association UK**

The timing of Seat At The Table was so perfect, it made everyone on the AMA-UK all sit up and think much harder about where we were and what we needed to improve, we knew we had a gender balance sorted but we hadn't put nearly enough focus on diversity and it has become a subject we always address now. It also highlighted the issues at a much larger scale in the music industry than just our own board - how can we be trying to make change at performance level when board level was still so antiquated and white male dominated - it felt like a huge wake up call to the industry - and it gave us a sense of real change and invigorated the industry for a better future.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Having a seat at the table is imperative for me as a hard working entrepreneur & black woman that wants to contribute value from my positive experiences and achievements with my fellow black women whom are also on their growth journeys, destined for greatness in all that they aspire to.

Tamika Martin
Director & PR Consultant
Ucreate PR & Events
Management Ltd.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

It means being part of the change, and leaving a legacy.

Tomi Oyewumi

**Equity Diversity and
Inclusion Partner
PPL**

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Being present, ensuring the opportunity to represent ALL women, to challenge legislation and not be intimidated by male presence when decisions are made.

Hannah Joseph

Director & Music consultant

Decibelle ltd

Westminster Uni

365 Artists

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Ruth Barlow

**Director of Live Licensing
Beggars Group
AIM Board**

It's a reflection of what I have achieved in my career. Having the opportunity to be part of shaping the organisations I'm involved with, be heard and able to offer a point view. I'm very mindful that I have to be active and add value and importantly remind myself that I have been invited to participate, so I take each responsibility very seriously.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Martha Bolton
Digital Marketing Manager
AEI Group

One of my personal mantras is ‘representation breeds participation’. Diversity in positions of power leads to participation from the minorities that are being represented.

It’s incredibly empowering to look at the places you want to go and see that people who look like you are already there, and are taking up space.

When we see reflections of ourselves seated at the table we are able to dream that one day we might sit there too.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

**Rhyana Tamara
Ebanks-Babb**

**Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
Manager
Human rights charity**

Having a seat at the table means that you can authentically bring your individual value you have within, for the betterment of the cause, project, work that you do. Having your voice valued and heard is so vital not only for selfhood but for those who are impacted by that very table. I believe that if you can't have a seat at whatever table you are trying to get your feet under, create your own table and find those who can bring the chairs, the full meal, dessert and After Eights too!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Eve Horne

**Founder/ Singer-
Songwriter/ Producer/
Campaigner
PeakMusicUK**

I hope to be a role model for young women of colour, shouting as loud as I can for those who follow behind me. It's my purpose and my duty to make sure the women of our future understand they have a choice and, when they make that choice, they feel comfortable and confident in the environment that they are passionate about working in.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Meike Nolte

Head of Artist Services

Beatport

It is shocking to see the lack of diversity in leadership positions within the music industry. Diversity should be an integral part of every business and needs to come from the top down. It is important to change systemic discrimination and biases, especially in an industry that is so global and diverse. We need to establish more role models and lead by good example!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

**Paige Michel-
Strachan**

**Social Media Assistant
Carnival Village Trust**

To me, having a seat at the table means (i) being acknowledged and respected (ii) the opportunity to have my thoughts and feelings heard (iii) the power to make decisions and implement positive change.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Daniella Spadini
Singer-Songwriter

Having a seat at the table is having a more complete human experience represented in every boardroom, every writing session, and every moment where decisions are made.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Vicki McCall

**Head of National Radio
Promotions
Listen Up**

Having a Seat at the Table (to me) means fair representation and ensures there are diverse voices at every level, presenting a different perspective/point of view. It's vital we work together to build a more inclusive culture, have difficult conversations but bring about change, as it all impacts the wider music industry.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Suzanne Lachapelle

**Finance Director
Cooking Vinyl Group
AIM Board**

This report shines a bright light on how skewed the music industry board rooms are with respect to gender and ethnicity. Having worked in a corporate environment for 20 years prior to joining the music industry 6 years ago, I have witnessed how it's a prevalent, almost normal, occurrence for the majority of board rooms to look a certain way. Having a "Seat at the Table" for me means being seen, heard and respected for our ideas and opinions, surrounded by open-mindedness and collaboration.

The report's importance in highlighting this imbalance can't be ignored. Gender and ethnicity should be a given on our Boards. Being part of this conversation, being a leader at an independent record label and having a seat on the AIM Board are just small parts of how I can provide support and make sure that these kinds of reports are no longer required in the near future.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

When decisions are made, whether big or small, it is important that each party affected has a say in this decision. This is what representation, or a 'Seat at the Table', means to me.

Lotje Horvers
Tour Manager
Ghostlight Productions

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Madelon Lissidini

**Marketing Manager
Amazon**

Having a seat at the table gives us first-hand opportunities to actively critique and change the systems by which we continue to operate as business driven society. It allows us to confront the processes that are carried out by stakeholders and provide more diverse and innovative solutions to day-to-day and future challenges.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Sara Al Hamad

CEO / Founder

Rika Muzika Ltd

Having a Seat at the Table means I can challenge those in the position of power without the fear of being silenced. Due to my specific personal circumstances it was always very difficult to get into the room, let alone to join the table, but nothing defeats the overwhelming joy when you finally take your seat and leave the door wide open for many like you to follow.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

It's super important because it's a chance for women to have a bigger influence on important issues that also affect us!

Wardah Sempa

Editor

Link Up TV

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Having a seat at the table means knowing that when important decisions are made there's a person who can advocate for you in the room who might have experienced similar barriers to you. Barriers which they may not have faced as a more privileged person. Those decisions impact careers, lives and the wider society. We welcome the reports, and want to champion organisations who are committed to making changes.

Vanessa Threadgold

Artist Manager
JVO Management /
Cactus City Studio

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Vicky Pasion

Founder

Gifted, by Nature

A Seat at the Table means unapologetically taking up space - having the privilege to use my voice, gifts and vision for the people in my community, who look like me and have had similar experiences; it's powerful to be a person at the table that you wish you saw when you were growing up.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Lia Lieghio

**Music Manager / Head of
Music
Eight Music & HearOne**

A seat at the table to me means more opportunities to collaborate and learn, for everyone involved. I've seen first hand the power of when the underrepresented come together and It's something that needs more space, more encouragement and more attention!

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Having a broader prospective and sharing the voices of the unheard. Having a seat at the table for me would mean increasing the percentage of black women producers in the music industry and inspiring others to aspire to increase that number too.

Renee Rain Thomas

Music Producer & Songwriter

TheGoddessMusic

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

It means that my voice and the voice of the female creators that I represent will be heard. Women contribute an incredible amount of time, energy and skill to all facets of the music industry. It's time we had a seat at every table!

Monica Corton

CEO & Founder

Go to Eleven Entertainment

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Claire Rose
Outreach Manager
PRS for Music

A Seat at the Table, to me, is a catalyst for effective change within the music industry. It's an extremely powerful tool that should be used to hold organisations to account who aren't making necessary changes to make a more healthy, diverse and powerful industry.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Maya Kalev

**Label Manager,
UK & Europe
Stones Throw Records/
AIM Board**

Being a member of the AIM Board has given me a real insight into a diverse range of musical companies with varying approaches to the challenges facing independent music businesses today, at a time when being reactive and flexible is more important than ever. Being a part of an industry body helping to shape the conversation around some of the key issues continues to be an invaluable experience.

The Aim board is currently made up of over 50% female members, and I encourage all people from marginalised genders who are interested in participating in some of these discussions and learning from their peers in the industry to apply to join.

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Being a care experienced Black woman with a seat at the table, means that others with a similar lived experience, can be encouraged that they are valuable and can 100% create their own destiny too!

Annie Gibbs
Founder
Amour Destine CIC

”

What does having a Seat at the Table mean to you?

“

Evelyn Ong
Music Video Director

It means having equal opportunity compared to my counterparts in the industry, no matter their creed, colour, race and history. Having to work harder for the same jobs has made me more entrepreneurial and forced me to have a strong work ethic, but I have also had potential opportunities taken away because of attributes I cannot control. Having a Seat at the Table means having the best entities, people and teams to create an honest representation of those in the creative industry, to empower future, multi-cultural generations.

”